

POTENTIAL TARGET COLUMNS FOR DATA SUBMITTED TO WP2 ATLANTECO-BASE

The fields/ column headers suggested below stem from the 13 DarwinCore essential variables (template available at: <https://github.com/gbif/ipt/wiki/occurrenceData#templates> ; see also <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc.htm>) to which we added fields we believed essential for adequately reporting, verifying and disseminating the data synthesized within WP2. This is product of discussions among several AtlantECO partners, within and outside of WP2. Main members involved in the creation of the present template were:

- Meike Vogt
- Stéphane Pesant
- Hugo Sarmiento
- Fabio Benedetti
- Pieter Provoost
- ...

Overarching fields

1. **ProjectID**: Name of the overarching project (AtlantECO_H2020_GA#210591007) - Maybe not necessary.
2. **ProjectWP**: Work Package within the overarching project (WP2,WP4 etc.) - Maybe useful for internal use only.
3. **DataSilo**: Name of data silo within WP (plastics, carbon, metaG, microscopy, imaging etc.) - Maybe useful for internal use only.
4. **ContactName**: String with names of the people in charge of the dataset (Meike Vogt, Fabio Benedetti, Hugo Sarmiento, Erik Van Sebille etc.) - at least 2.
5. **ContactAdress**: String with the valid email addresses of the people in ContactName.
6. **occurrenceID**: AtlantECO-specific identifier to be defined (occurrenceID from the original data sources are reported in the 'Source identifying fields' and will thus be retained, when given, to ensure traceability). To define the AtlantECO ID, we may need to construct one from some of the other fields suggested here (e.g. concatenate values given in columns 3+7+8+12+36+49+50 and separate them by an underscore to generate a character string).

Positional fields

7. **decimalLatitude**: Geographic Latitude in decimal degree, following the -180/+180 WGS84 Spatial Reference System (SRS).
8. **decimalLongitude**: Geographic Longitude in decimal degree, following the -180/+180 WGS84 SRS.
9. **geodeticDatum**: SRS of the spatial coordinates; give WGS84 only.
10. **CoordUncertainty**: Uncertainty estimate of the decimal coordinates; **in meters**.
11. **CountryCode**: **ISO3166-1-alpha-2 code** for the country the observations belongs to.
12. **eventDate**: Date of the sampling event. OBIS recommends using the extended ISO 8601 format with hyphens (e.g. 'YYYY-MM-DD'). If possible, add time of the day, after

the data, as follows: 'THH:MM:SS' (e.g. '2017-09-23T12:04:23'). If time of the day was not recorded, then just add 'T00:00:00'.

13. **eventDateInterval**: Numeric values indicating the duration of the **in situ sampling event** (not the time spent in the lab analyzing the sample).
14. **eventDateIntervalUnit**: Unit of **eventDateInterval** (e.g. seconds, minutes, hours, light-years...).
15. **Year**: Year of the sampling event (**YYYY format**).
16. **Month**: Month of the sampling event (**MM format**).
17. **Day**: Day of the sampling event (**DD format**).
18. **Bathymetry**: Depth of the seafloor at sampling event, **in meters**, ≤ 0 . Will help us inform whether the observation stems from a coastal environment or not.
19. **BathySource**: String indicating whether Bathymetry was measured at sampling event or inferred a posteriori from NOAA or GEBCO based on the spatial coordinates (e.g., 'GEBCO', or 'NOAA' or 'In situ').
20. **HabitatType**: String indicating the type of habitat the sample was taken from (e.g. open ocean water column, river plume, river, coral reef, mangrove...)
21. **LonghurstProvince**: Longhurst Province the sample was taken from (one of 56 possible four-letter geocodes, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Longhurst_code). Can be attributed a posteriori from <https://github.com/thechisholmlab/Longhurst-Province-Finder>.
22. **Depth**: Sample depth (**in meters below the local sea surface**); > 0 ; $= 0$ is surface.
23. **DepthAccuracy**: Single term that describes the accuracy of the collection depth, **in meters** (not sure here?).
24. **DepthIntegral**: Depth span below sea surface, **in meters**; > 0 ; $= 0$ if surface.
25. **MinDepth**: minimum depth for depth-integrated quantities, **in meters**, > 0 .
26. **MaxDepth**: maximum depth for depth-integrated quantities, **in meters**, > 0 .

Source identifying fields

27. **ParentEventID**: Describes the parent event, which is composed of one or more sub-sampling (child) events (eventID below). (e.g. AMT29, Tara Oceans st.75, CPR tow XX etc.)
28. **eventID**: Labels the replicate samples (or sub-samples) from a ParentEventID (e.g. a sample number from a station if multiple samples were taken at same sampling station). **Make sure each replicate sample receives a unique eventID**, which could be based on the unique sample ID in your dataset.
29. **InstitutionCode**: Custodian institution for the data record (ex: IMEV, MBA, UU, FUSP etc.).
30. **SourceArchive**: Describes the online archive where the data is stored (e.g. PANGAEA, OBIS, GBIF, DRYAD etc.).
31. **OrigCollectionCode**: Code given to the collection or the dataset within the SourceArchive (e.g. the code given to the CPR collection in OBIS/GBIF).
32. **OrigCollectionID**: occurrenceID given to the record/measurement in the SourceArchive. Retained to ensure traceability.
33. **BiblioCitation**: String indicating the bibliographic citation associated with the data

(when possible; can be a dataset, a paper, a report).

34. **BiblioCitationDOI**: DOI of the bibliographic citation (when possible).

35. **DateDataAccess**: Date at which the data was downloaded from the SourceArchive; in the ISO 8601 format (e.g. YYYY-MM-DD). Time of the day not needed.

Observation Classification fields (not applicable for measurements other than biological plankton groups, or needs to be adjusted)

36. **OrigScientificName**: Scientific name of the plankton taxon/observation as reported in the source dataset. Might already be the correct one.

37. **ScientificName**: Corrected scientific name of the taxon, as given in WoRMS.

38. **WoRMS_ID**: Uniform resource identifier issued from WoRMS for the biological taxon recorded. Not sure if the **aphiaID** is enough or if you require the **Life Science Identifier** (LSID). For instance, for *Centropages typicus* the aphiaID is 104499 and the LSID is simply 'urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:104499'. So the **aphiaID seems enough** (<https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=webservice>).

39. **TaxonRank**: Taxonomic rank at which the taxon was identified and recorded (e.g. species, family, order...).

40. **Kingdom**: Either 'Animalia' (aphiaID #2), 'Plantae' (#3), 'Fungi' (#4), 'Protozoa' (#5), 'Bacteria' (#6), 'Chromista' (#7), or 'Archaea' (#8).

41. **Phylum**: Phylum of the taxon recorded.

42. **Order**: Order of the taxon recorded.

43. **Class**: Class of the taxon recorded.

44. **Family**: Family of the taxon recorded.

45. **Genus**: Genus of the taxon recorded.

46. **Species**: Species name of the taxon recorded.

47. **Subspecies**: Subspecies, or variety, of the taxon recorded.

48. **LifeForm**: The type of population organisation- and the ecological organisation of the organism recorded (e.g. "singular", "colonial", "symbiotic", "free living" etc.).

49. **AssocTaxa**: The function and scientific name of any taxon associated with the biological unit recorded (e.g. "HOST_Rhizosolenia").

Measurement fields (type, quantity and methodology)

50. **measurementID**: Identifier for the measurement or fact (information pertaining to measurements, facts, characteristics, or assertions). May be a global unique identifier or an identifier specific to the data set. **Not sure what this is supposed to be?**

51. **measurementType**: The nature of the measurement, fact, characteristic, or assertion (e.g. presence, absence, length, size, abundance, concentration, microplastic counts, carbon flux rate etc.).

52. **measurementTypeID**: An identifier for the measurementType (global unique identifier, URI). The identifier should reference the measurementType in a vocabulary. Where possible, use an URI to identify the quantity you want to describe (e.g. S1228 for 'copies of the nifHgene', or S1230 for 'blood'). List of URIs available here: <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S12/current/> . **But it seems like many URI will**

need to be added to this list to cover all the types of data/records/measurements to be gathered within WP2. For instance, there is yet no URI for 'plankton organism', or 'microplastic'. We may need to gather all the measurementType labels found in the WP2 datasets a posteriori (i.e. just before final dataset submission) and create a new NERC URI for all of them, and then inform the measurementTypeID header based on that?

53. **measurementValue**: The numeric value of the measurement, fact, characteristic, or assertion (e.g. '42' for a microscope count, or '1' for an occurrence, '0' for an absence etc.). No units.
54. **measurementUnit**: The unit associated with the measurementValue. Recommended best practice is to use the International System of Units (SI). Examples: m, mg, cells.m⁻³, mgC.m⁻³...
55. **measurementAccuracy**: Numeric value of the potential error associated with the measurementValue. Must be in same unit.
56. **measurementValueID**: An identifier for facts stored in the column measurementValue (global unique identifier, URI). This identifier can reference a controlled vocabulary (e.g. for sampling instrument names, methodologies, life stages). When the measurementValue refers to a value and not to a fact, the measurementvalueID has no meaning and should remain empty. *Not sure what URI to give here (no official list or source?).*
57. **Biomass_mgCm3**: Biomass in unit of carbon (mgC/m3) corresponding to the measurement.
58. **BiomassConvFactor**: Biomass conversion factor. If too complex conversion with multiple equations, indicate a conversion table, reference, or published data set...
59. **basisOfRecord**: Nature of the data record (e.g. 'preserved specimen', 'fossil specimen', 'living specimen' etc.).
60. **SamplingProtocol**: Indicates the sampling protocol used to make the measurement.
61. **SampleAmount**: Numeric value indicating the volume, or mass, of sample analysed to make the measurement (e.g. a volume of seawater filtered).
62. **SampleAmountUnit**: Unit corresponding to the SampleAmount (e.g. liter, ml, m3...).
63. **SampleEffort**: Indicates the time spent looking for an organism, or the area covered, the number of transect etc. So more of an indicator of sampling effort through time.
64. **DeterminedBy**: Name(s) of the people, groups or organizations who made the measurement, or identified the organism.
65. **DeterminedDate**: The date on which the measurement/identification was made (can differ from the eventDate).
66. **Note**: Any note or comment on the measurement event (e.g. 'Potential contamination', 'Heavy net clogging', 'Rough sea' etc.).

Environmental metadata fields (will heavily depend on metadata given with the data though; we could also provide the closest climatological value a posteriori using WOA18, GlobColour, AVISO or COPERNICUS products?)

67. **Surf_temperature**: Sea surface temperature in Celsius (usually closest satellite

measurement?).

68. **Temperature**: Temperature measured in **Celsius** at sampling event (day and depth resolved).

69. **Surf_salinity**: Same as above but for salinity.

70. **Salinity**: -

71. **Surf_nitrate_micromol**: Same as above but for Nitrates (NO_3) concentration, in micromolar (μM).

72. **Nitrate_micromol**: -

73. **Surf_phosphate_micromol**: Same as above but for Phosphates (PO_4^{3-}) concentration, in micromolar (μM).

74. **Phosphate_micromol**: -

75. **Surf_Chla_mgm3**: Same as above but for Chlorophyll-a concentration, in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

76. **Chla_mgm3**:

77....

78. **Flag**: Notes on quality/uncertainty of occurrence/measurement (e.g. quality-control flags, uncertainty, errors, contamination issues, taxonomic uncertainty, etc.).

NOTES

- Value for missing data (header could have been informed/ measured but was not) = 'NA'
- Value when header is just not applicable to observations = 'Not_applicable'

